

Effect of insecticides on *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* spore germination, IRRI, 1983.

Insecticide	Spore germination ^a (%)			
	Insecticide mixed with media ^b		Insecticide on media surface ^c	
	<i>M. anisopliae</i>	<i>B. bassiana</i>	<i>M. anisopliae</i>	<i>B. bassiana</i>
	<i>Recommended for BPH control^d</i>			
Monocrotophos	0 c	32 b	72 b	95 b
BPMC	1 b	2 c	36 d	36 d
Carbosulfan	0 c	0 d	66 c	68 c
Azinphos ethyl + BPMC	0 c	0 d	28 e	68 c
No insecticide	99 a	100 a	99 a	100 a
Insecticide mean	0	9	51	67
	<i>Causing BPH resurgence^e</i>			
Azinphos ethyl	20 d	71 c	16 d	77 c
Deltamethrin	56 c	90 b	81 b	89 b
Methyl parathion	0 e	6 e	15 d	72 d
MIPC	66 b	38 d	75 c	67 e
No insecticide	99 a	100 a	99 a	100 a
Insecticide mean	36	51	47	77

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. 300 random spores counted 24 h after insecticide application. ^bInsecticide mixed with the culture media at 40-45°C, then plated. Fungal spore suspension (0.3 ml/petri dish) was spread on the cooled and hardened media. ^cInsecticides and fungi spores were mixed together in suspension and 0.3 ml/petri dish was spread on top of the hardened culture media. ^dAt the national recommended rate of 0.75 kg ai/ha. ^eAt the minimal rate that causes resurgence (0.50 kg ai/ha, except deltamethrin at 0.025 kg ai/ha).

Influence of flooding, fertilizer, and plant spacing on insect pest incidence

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We studied the influence of cultural methods on reducing insect pest incidence in rice in 1981 kuruvai.

Continuous flooding and alternate flooding and draining; 15- × 10-cm, 20-

× 10-cm, and 30- × 10-cm spacing (water regimes and spacings were main plots); 50, 100, and 150 kg N/ha; and 42 and 83 kg K/ha (N and K treatments were sub-plots) were tested in a split-plot design with 3 replications. TKM9 was planted in 1 6-m² plots. Tillers and silvershoots were counted in 19 randomly chosen hills/plot 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT). Populations of green leafhopper (GLH) and brown planthopper (BPH), and whorl maggot (WM) damaged leaves on 10 hills/

Insect population and grain yield as determined by cultural practice, Aduthurai, India.^a

Treatment	GLH/10 hills	BPH/10 hills	WM (% damaged leaves)	GM (% silvershoots)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Water management</i>					
Continuous flooding	19 b	9 b	7 b	2a	5.6 a
Alternate flooding and draining	13 a	4a	4a	3 b	4.9 b
<i>Spacing</i>					
15 × 10 cm	13 a	6	5	3	5.0
20 × 10 cm	18 b	6	6	2	5.2
30 × 10 cm	18 b	6	5	3	5.5
<i>N level</i>					
50 kg/ha	15 a	3a	5	2	4.8 b
100 kg/ha	16 a	7 b	5	2	5.2 b
150 kg/ha	18 b	8 c	5	3	5.7 a
<i>K level</i>					
42 kg/ha	17	6	5	2	5.2
83 kg/ha	16	6	5	3	5.3

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

cides. Recommended insecticides reduced spore germination more than resurgence-causing insecticides did, probably because a higher dosage of the recommended insecticide was applied.

Because both types of insecticides greatly inhibited spore germination of both fungi, it is unlikely that insecticides cause resurgence by counteracting the beneficial effect of entomogenous fungi. Among the BPH resurgence-causing insecticides, deltamethrin, the most powerful, had the weakest effect on spore germination. Only methyl parathion, the second most powerful BPH resurgence-causing insecticide, greatly reduced spore germination. □

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plot were counted 20, 45, and 70 DT. Grain yield was recorded.

Alternate flooding and draining significantly reduced GLH and BPH populations and WM damage. The 10- × 15-cm spacing reduced GLH numbers (see table). The BPH population increased with N application. K did not influence insect damage or grain yield. Increased gall midge (GM) incidence in plots with intermittent flooding may have been caused by a change in microclimate, and yield reduction may have been caused by hardening of the soil. □

Effect of organophosphatic insecticides on the yellow stem borer (YSB) eggs and parasites

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Insecticides used in rice fields often kill nontarget insect species. We studied the effect of seven insecticides on YSB eggs and egg parasite *Telenomus dignoides* Nixon (Hymenoptera, Scelionidae). Field